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- Poetry
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“UNEXPECTED LESSONS FROM THE OTHER SIDE OF THE DESK”

I never imagined I would ever play the role of a class adviser – even once.

I began my teaching career as a floating teacher at my high school alma mater, so I wasn't accustomed to having an advisory class. However, I witnessed how stressed my fellow teachers were back then because of their advisory responsibilities. They always had this moment when they couldn't even have a proper lunch at school or enjoy their weekends because of the demands their advisory class put on them. I never wanted to experience the stress and demands that my fellow teachers faced.

Things changed, however, when I transferred to my current workstation. It was September 2021, and the entire country was under the restrictions brought on by the COVID-19 pandemic when what I feared the most happened—I was assigned to be the class adviser of one of the sections in Grade 10, and given my situation as a new teacher, I had no choice but to accept the task. I remember how challenging that time was, and because we were physically apart, I believed my primary responsibility was to ensure they felt supported by a class adviser, despite our lack of in-person interaction.

My days went smoothly, addressing their minor issues such as a slow internet connection and late submission of requirements to their subject teachers due to unforeseen circumstances at home. Gradually, my perspective on having an advisory class shifted as a result of their influence. I learned to love what I was doing back then, and I'm glad that my first advisory class appreciated even the simplest things I did for them. I cannot imagine how we formed such a strong connection even if we never physically met and only conducted classes and “Kumustahan Sessions” in Google Meet. That bond permanently changed how I look at being an adviser.

During my second year of teaching at my current workstation, I experienced how having an advisory class feels in a face-to-face setting. I honestly felt a wide range of emotions during that time. I must admit, the whole school year was a challenge. At first, we didn't move along, possibly due to my attachment to my previous advisory class and their distinct vibe. They're not difficult to advise, actually. They will follow whatever I say, knowing that I will never ask them to do something that will put them in a negative situation.

I've faced many challenges as a class adviser, but only one tested my integrity and the bond we shared. The majority of the class got involved in an issue of dishonesty during their third quarterly exam, and the worst part is that some of their classmates, who had no intention to be involved, got dragged into the situation because of how the unfortunate deed happened in the class.

At the time, I was left feeling betrayed and unsure of how to react. I cannot sleep properly for a week straight. I continuously questioned myself where I went wrong in guiding and advising them. I was disappointed; I never imagined they could commit such an act. We never had a problem for almost 7 months that we were at school, yet they committed such actions when the school year was about to end. However, even if I was disheartened by what happened, nothing compares to the pain I felt when I saw them crying, stressed, and depressed because of what happened to the class. The usual classroom, full of happiness and pleasant vibes, suddenly turned gloomy and quiet.

I became afraid of what they could commit because of the pain, regret, and fear they felt at the time. I recognize that I am not particularly skilled at providing comfort to individuals during their difficult moments; however, I acted as I felt was necessary at that time. The heart of being an adviser prevailed over me because I knew that that was the time they needed me the most. I maintained constant communication with them and cooperated with the prefect of discipline to settle everything. They faced the consequences of their actions. But at that time, things are already clear to them: they committed an act of dishonesty, and that's why they have to face whatever consequences it will bring.

That particular mistake taught them many lessons. Despite the immense pain and suffering they endured, they learned a crucial life lesson: always consider the consequences of your actions before committing them, and if you can't bear the weight, reconsider. They often say that the students will learn from the teacher. That's true, but in my case, I also learned a lot from my students. They taught me many lessons that I don't think I would have ever learned if they had not become my advisory class. These experiences fueled my passion for teaching and nurturing more students under my guidance.

I know that as time goes by, more challenges and struggles may come my way as a teacher and class adviser. But as long as the fire within me keeps burning, I will stay faithful to my vocation and fulfill my calling.